

Preliminary Identification of Future Needs with respect to Heavy Liquid Metal Core and Pool Thermal Hydraulics

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INTRODUCTION

In Europe, an important role is recognized for fast reactors, since they will enable the closure of the fuel cycle, which is necessary for a sustainable and responsible use of the natural resources being provided by our planet. There are several fast reactor designs under development in Europe. Within this paper, the focus will be on two heavy liquid metal cooled fast reactor designs, i.e. the lead-bismuth cooled MYRRHA design and the lead-cooled ALFRED design. The MYRRHA design is described extensively by [1], while [2] describes the ALFRED design. Both designs are pool type reactors, however their pool configurations are significantly different. This is also true for the core and fuel assembly designs, with the ALFRED design aiming at deploying grid-spaced fuel assemblies, while the MYRRHA design aims at wire-wrapped fuel assemblies. Both design projects are supported by a long-standing series of collaborative projects sponsored by the European Commission, allowing to build and bring together the European expertise coordinating and streamlining the R&D efforts in all disciplines necessary for the design teams.

The collaborative ANSELMUS project was initiated with the single objective to support the deployment of heavy liquid metal cooled advanced reactors in Europe. One of the specific objectives is to assess fuel assembly safety by experiment and modelling. The project started in September 2022 and aims to be finalized in August 2026.

The collaborative TRANSPARANT project aims to take the next step towards industrialization required to close the fuel cycle. In the field of thermal hydraulics, the specific objective is to describe the state-of-the-art and define a current best fit approach for thermal hydraulic analysis of important heavy liquid metal cooled reactor components and systems, including the fuel bundle and the primary pool. The project started in September 2024 and aims to be finalized in November 2028.

Through these projects, the European experimental infrastructure from the Von Karman Institute, SCK CEN, KIT and ENEA, can be coupled to the numerical modelling

expertise of NRG PALLAS, CRS4, ENEA and the Von Karman Institute. The collaborations are depicted in Fig. 1.

Topic	Experiment	Simulation Organisation(s)
Fuel Assembly	NACIE liquid metal 	NRG PALLAS ENEA CRS4 VON KARMAN INSTITUTE FOR FLUID DYNAMICS
	AUPINEL water 	NRG PALLAS VON KARMAN INSTITUTE FOR FLUID DYNAMICS
	KALLA liquid metal 	NRG PALLAS KIT
Pool	MYRRHAbelle water facility 	NRG PALLAS VON KARMAN INSTITUTE FOR FLUID DYNAMICS CRS4
	ESCAPE liquid metal facility 	NRG PALLAS sck cen VON KARMAN INSTITUTE FOR FLUID DYNAMICS

Figure 1: Integration of experimental and modelling expertise

This paper intends to focus on the preliminary conclusions from the state-of-the-art assessments and identification of future needs. Additionally, the linked ongoing activities with respect to core and pool thermal hydraulics will be described.

In the following section, the core thermal hydraulics activities will be described, followed by a section in which the pool thermal hydraulics activities will be mentioned. Finally, conclusions and an outlook are provided.

CORE THERMAL HYDRAULICS

Assessing the State-of-the-Art and Future Needs

A lot of work was performed on fuel assembly thermal hydraulics in the past two decades, both in European collaborative projects and internationally by various companies and institutes. Therefore, it was decided to gather

the European experts in the field of wire-wrapped fuel assemblies (since this activity is being sponsored by the TRANSPARENT project with a focus on MYRRHA) and assess the status of the work performed defining the state-of-the-art, and to identify and prioritize the future needs. This process started with a one-day workshop in March 2025. Within this workshop, the European experts in the field reached preliminary conclusions. Together with the identification of challenges that was presented in the textbook on ‘Thermal Hydraulics Aspects of Liquid Metal Cooled Nuclear Reactors’ [3], the following preliminary conclusions were drawn:

- There is sufficient knowledge regarding the flow and heat transport behavior under non-deformed nominal conditions. Simulations are sufficiently accurate in view of the available safety margins.
- Upper bounds for the accuracy in the prediction of the peak cladding temperature are known. The most effective path forward to reduce these bounds is related to a better understanding of velocity profiles.
- Characterization of the effect of deformations of the pins and/or the wrapper remains an open question. It is now clear that, even if the current efforts turn out to be successful, the variety of possible deformations is too large to draw definite conclusions.
- Flow blockages are being studied, but there is a mismatch between Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation results and experimental results which is only partly understood. Hence, a deeper investigation is needed.
- Detection of flow blockages or deformations leading to increased peak temperatures is a challenge.
- Complete core simulation in which the effect of the inter-wrapper or bypass flow is taken into account is still a challenge.
- In severe accident studies in which fuel relocates and accumulates in low flow zones, cooling evaluation is a challenge. This may require development and validation of simulation methods for large particles, e.g. Discrete Element Modelling (DEM) combined with CFD.
- The effect of (partial) wetting on heat transfer is mostly neglected and not understood.
- A start has been made to study the possible impact of chemistry effects on the flow and heat transfer. Numerical models and codes are being developed but need confirmation by further experimental data.
- Flow induced vibrations in the core are experimentally shown to have a negligible role in the MYRRHA design. However, the experiments were design specific and this conclusion might not be true for other liquid metal fast reactor fuel assembly designs.

All participants agree that for every topic, it is of high importance to bring experimentalists and numerical experts close together and have them collaborate.

Deformations

Within the ANSELMUS and TRANSPARENT projects, a variety of activities are devoted to the assessment of the effect of fuel pin deformations on the heat transport in the core. Both grid-spaced and wire-wrapped design are being studied. A recent summary of these efforts is available in [4].

Grid Spaced Bundles

For grid-spaced bundles, an experiment is being performed in the Italian NACIE facility at ENEA [5]. The experiment will be performed with pure lead as coolant. Within the test section, three of the nineteen pins will be deformed at strategically located positions (corner, edge and internal) and the adjacent subchannels will be instrumented with thermocouples. The experiments are planned for 2025. A blind simulation effort was performed prior to the execution of the experiments, to be published soon.

Wire-wrapped Bundles

With respect to wire-wrapped bundles, two experiments are being performed. One with water as working fluid and one with lead-bismuth as working fluid. The water facility AUPINEL at VKI in Belgium is a new facility aiming at validation of the flow field. A description is available in [4]. The test section, in which the rods will be pre-deformed, is still under design with support from numerical simulations. The lead-bismuth facility THESYS is located in the KALLA laboratory in Germany. The KALLA laboratory, its loops and previous test sections, e.g. for undeformed wire-wrapped fuel assembly experiments, are described in [6]. Within the experiment, a seven pin bundle is used of which the center pin can be rotated together with its wire making space for one of the corner pins to be pushed inward by a piston while the bundle is inserted. This allows measurement of various amounts of deformation, up to pin-to-pin contact. However, the exact shape of the deformation can't be measured. Therefore, in addition a mock-up experiment was performed under the conditions foreseen in the loop. At a given position of the piston, the mock-up is drained and filled with epoxy. Subsequently, the mock-up bundle is cut into slabs. The surfaces are then polished in order to determine with sufficient precision the shape of the deformation.

Figure 2: Cutting of the mock-up in progress, showing an unpolished and polished cross section with the center pin rotated.

Figure 2 shows the mock-up cut into pieces (left), an unpolished (center) and a polished (right) surface. Once all the surfaces have been polished, the deformed bundle shape will be reconstructed in 3D CAD and will be provided to the simulation experts.

POOL THERMAL HYDRAULICS

Assessing the State-of-the-Art and Future Needs

Similar to the case of fuel assembly thermal hydraulics, the TRANSPARANT project gathers European experts in the field of pool thermal hydraulics to discuss the state-of-the-art and the future challenges in this field. This process started with a one-day workshop in March 2025. Within the workshop, European experts came to preliminary conclusions, which are presented below together with challenges identified in the ‘Thermal Hydraulics Aspects of Liquid Metal Cooled Nuclear Reactors’ [3]:

- To obtain better experimental data, liquid metal flow measurement techniques, including Contactless Inductive Flow Tomography (CIFT) and Ultrasound Doppler Velocimetry (UDV) need development.
- In the design of (combined effect) test facilities, attention should be paid to the characterization of the installation (weight, surface finish, insulation, instrumentation type and positions, heat losses...) to enable accurate boundary condition and initial condition definitions in simulations.
- In general, models need to be developed and validated for large components present in a pool. Pump and core models have been studied extensively and their limitations are understood. Best practice guidelines for modelling such components are being developed. Likewise, CFD or multi-scale coupled simulations for heat exchangers need further development and validation.
- Additional validation data will be welcome. Currently, model validation relies on a very limited set of data, very often with large uncertainties, caused by inherent difficulties brought by the liquid opacity and temperature of exercise. The use of high-resolution numerical data (e.g. using Large Eddy Simulation (LES) or Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) approaches) can be considered.
- Model development and validation for stratification and fatigue damage need attention.
- The size of the pool and the small length scales of some of the phenomena to be studied, theoretically require very small mesh sizes leading to huge mesh counts. It should be checked whether the stringent theoretical mesh requirements can be released and if so, up till what point.

- The cooling of internals and the vessel wall (inside and outside) requires development of turbulent heat transfer models which are applicable to all flow conditions, since the flow in a large pool may encompass the full range of flow regimes, from forced, through mixed, to natural convection. Such models need validation through dedicated experiments and will strongly profit from additional high resolution (LES and/or DNS) simulation data.
- Model development is needed for chemical interactions and the effect impurities may have on the flow and heat transport.
- Preliminary studies have been made to assess the effects of sloshing, e.g. induced by an earthquake or a pressure wave resulting from a heat exchanger tube rupture. The results are design dependent and therefore need deeper investigation per design.
- Even though gas entrainment seems to play a smaller role for heavy liquid metal reactor pools than e.g. for sodium fast reactor pools, its occurrence and impact need attention.
- Preliminary experimental and CFD studies for solidification in a lead pool have been performed. No severe safety criticality could be substantiated. Even though solidification might not play a large role in the safety evaluation of a reactor, for economic purposes, the occurrence and consequences of solidification deserve to be studied.
- The state-of-the-art of the interaction between a heavy liquid metal and water needs to be established and the need for further studies and numerical model developments needs to be identified.
- Severe accidents in which the core melts have not been addressed a lot. The behavior of molten fuel in a heavy liquid metal core and pool needs to be studied to enhance understanding and allow model development.

Like in the case of fuel assembly thermal hydraulics, also for pool thermal hydraulics, all participants agree that for every topic, it is of high importance to bring experimentalists and numerical experts close together and have them collaborate.

Benchmarks

The TRANSPARANT project includes two benchmarks to further enhance the state-of-the-art with respect to pool thermal hydraulics. Two facilities are considered: MYRRHAbelle mainly focusing on the momentum validation and ESCAPE on thermal validation.

MYRRHAbelle

MYRRHAbelle is a plexiglass water mock-up of the MYRRHA reactor design version 1.2 on a 1/5 scale. The facility and former experiments are described by [7]. New experiments instrumented with Particle Image Velocimetry,

pressure taps and thermocouples are being planned aiming at provision of flow characterization enabled through the use of water as simulant fluid for validation of simulation approaches. After careful consideration with all involved partners, a single pump failure scenario was selected as benchmark. For this scenario, also data from the liquid metal ESCAPE facility is available from a previous European collaborative project enabling a direct comparison of flow behavior in the two facilities under similar operating conditions.

ESCAPE

ESCAPE is a liquid metal electric mock-up of the MYRRHA reactor design version 1.2 on a 1/6 scale. The facility and its scaling are described by [8]. Since the facility has started the process of decommissioning, no new experiments are foreseen. However, from the large available experimental dataset, a loss-of-flow combined with a partial loss-of-heat-sink scenario is selected. This is a combination of scenarios individually studied in previous European collaborative projects (PATRICIA and PASCAL).

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

This paper presents a preliminary assessment of European experts on the future needs in the field of core and pool thermal hydraulics. Many aspects have been mentioned and shortly explained in the paper. A short list is provided below:

- Development of measurement techniques in liquid metal, specifically for local velocity.
- Fuel assembly deformations and blockages
- Complete core (incl. bypass flow) simulation methods
- Fuel debris relocation
- Effect of wetting on flow and heat transfer
- Chemistry effects on flow and heat transfer
- Fluid Structure Interaction in the core and pool
- Development of best practices to support students, young professionals and other newcomers to the field
- Creation of additional validation data, experiments and/or high-resolution simulations targeting specific purposes
- Sloshing
- Gas entrainment
- Solidification
- Interaction between heavy liquid metal and water
- Consequences of a fuel melt severe accident in the core and pool

Next to these specific conclusions, all experts agree that the development and application of Uncertainty Quantification methods are essential for experimental data and numerical simulations. To the latter aspect, a distinction can be made to uncertainty quantification based on

experimental data and uncertainty quantification solely on numerical data when experimental data is absent for whatever reason. As stressed before, close collaboration between experimentalists and numerical experts is highly recommended and very often the key to success.

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